

Triple bottom line: Implications on Private Higher Education Institutions (PHEIs) In Malaysia

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Abstract: This paper is a review based on the triple bottom line (TBL) conceptual paradigm and its implications on private higher education institutions (PHEIs) for community development. Existing literature and analysis suggest that PHEIs need to participate in profitable relations with stakeholders, while integrating their visions and purposes into their management agenda. The TBL tends to have a positive impact on PHEIs in terms of brand reputation and trust on brand equity and loyalty. Adopting the TBL can enhance mutual trust, reduce protest and help improve the public image of PHEIs, which are expected to support the socioeconomic welfare of the community and preserve the natural environment, while striving to increase their profitability.

Keywords: private higher education institutions (PHEIs) university social responsibility, triple bottom line, Malaysia.

I. INTRODUCTION

According to Elkington (1994), sustainability can be based on the triple bottom line (TBL), which goes beyond the traditional measures of profits, return on investment and shareholder value to include environmental and social dimensions. The TBL enables firms to not only focus on comprehensive investment results, but also to capitalize on the interrelated dimensions of profits, people and the planet (three Ps). In other words, corporations can commit to measuring their social and environmental impacts, besides their financial performance or standard bottom line. Like corporations, private higher education institutions (PHEIs) can use the TBL components to conceptualize their social and environmental responsibilities, while ameliorating their negative impacts by integrating sustainable practices into their operations, including student enrolment, academic practices and facilities and building maintenance to positively impact society and the environment, besides increasing the profit margins. The purpose of this conceptual article is to explore the role of the TBL for PHEIs in overcoming their current challenges to achieve long-term success in terms of profitability, social responsibility and environmental sustainability.

With reference to the first bottom line (profitability), a firm's success heavily depends on its financial performance or the profit it generates for shareholders (Miller, 2020). In the context of PHEIs, strategic planning initiatives and crucial business decisions can aim to maximize profits, while reducing costs and mitigating risks. Previously, many PHEIs had solely focused on their financial impact and growth; however, many purpose-driven PHEIs nowadays are striving to bring positive change in the globalized world without affecting their financial performance. With reference to the second bottom

line (social responsibility), firms need to focus on their societal impact or their commitment to people (Miller, 2020). In the context of PHEIs, shareholder value has been used as an indicator of success, whereby they strive to generate value for those who own shares of the institution. Nevertheless, PHEIs that have increasingly embraced sustainability now often focus on creating value for all stakeholders impacted by their business decisions, including students, parents, staff and other community members. With reference to the third bottom line (planet), large corporations have contributed a staggering amount of environmental pollution, which has been a leading cause of climate change and environmental concerns (Miller, 2020). In the context of PHEIs, environmental preservation cannot solely be covered by large corporations; PHEIs also need to play their part to make changes to reduce the carbon footprint, for example, by utilizing ethically sourced materials, reduce energy consumption and streamline their business practices toward long-term sustainability.

II. SECONDARY FINDINGS

A. Economic, social and environmental bottom lines

Nowadays, the management of higher education institutions (HEIs) is getting increasingly corporate because they are expected to drive progress based on financial, social and environmental bottom lines (Puukka, 2008). HEIs have considerable direct and indirect economic impacts on the local and regional economies, for instance, their staff and students can increase consumer demand, the use of services and tax income in the region. By providing locally relevant skills and knowledge, they contribute to regional business innovation and employment. Moreover, financially sound HEIs also conduct their operations in a cost-effective way. Additionally, they have the social responsibility to protect and promote the wellbeing of staff and students, besides establishing favourable relationships with stakeholders. By investing in people, HEIs benefit in terms of staff loyalty and productivity. By adopting flexible reward policies, they can motivate staff to pursue novel entrepreneurial activities, such as knowledge transfer and regional engagement. By providing student support services and work-based learning opportunities, they can improve learning outcomes, enhance the learning experience and improve retention rates. By collaborating with local stakeholders, they can diversify their funding sources, leading to more research output and work-based learning opportunities. Further, HEIs are not only consumers of non-renewable energy, but are also sources of technological and organizational expertise needed to tackle socioenvironmental challenges. Their technology-based research, for example, the exploitation of geothermal energy and its incorporation into the wider community, helps embed environmental sustainability into the teaching and learning process.

Ekwueme, Egbunike and Innocent (2013) examined the relationship between sustainability reporting and corporate performance among 141 corporate managers, corporate employees, consumers and investors. Findings showed a positive relationship between sustainability reporting and corporate performance, whereby consumers and investors tend to patronize green corporations, resulting in their increased market share and market capitalization. Moreover, employees were found to choose green corporations that safeguard their interests and foster a healthy work environment, while corporate managers agreed that the cost of recycling is generally cheaper than new purchases.

Kappo-Abidemi and Kanayo (2020) asserted that HEI stakeholders now require institutions to comply with the TBL, especially in terms of community development. While profit making may not be applicable to government-funded HEIs, accountability is of great importance. Nevertheless, they still need to establish profitable relationships with stakeholders, while integrating their visions and purposes into their social agenda by collaborating with the diverse personalities with different levels of resource control. In brief, the TBL enables HEIs to establish community development programs that will increase mutual trust, increase support and reinforce their public image by integrating their socioeconomic welfare ventures and social environments to add value to community development.

Saeudy (2024) posited that the TBL can be applied to show sustainability as an organizing and controlling framework that can help HEIs to achieve long-term success. For example, PHEIs can adopt certain sustainability tools to reinforce their academic practices to become more sustainable for the current and future generations. These tools include sustainability themes that represent a wide array of institutional strides to assess the social, environmental and economic impact of their academic activities that can promote institutional prosperity and academic accountability in HEIs.

B. Change management and change leadership

Casey et al. (2014) asserted that academic library leaders need to adopt the TBL by integrating change management and change leadership. While change management allows them to deal with the project management elements of proposed innovations, change leadership requires them to examine the practical aspects of embarking on a new venture, such as changes in finances and accounting, personnel distribution and novel ways of doing business. While most organizational leaders handle change management well, many often overlook change leadership due to their overemphasis on the rational and cognitive aspects of an innovative venture, thus causing many of their change initiatives to fail. Two fundamental elements to transitioning to a culture of sustainability in academic libraries are (1) integrating sustainable values, strategies, principles, metrics and practices into the core business plans of the library and (2) developing leaders who will wholeheartedly support the sustainability initiatives. In brief, leaders should set the direction and demonstrate a positive and enthusiastic introduction to elicit stronger buy-in from stakeholders. They should also use the language of a particular organizational environment (for example, an academic library) when communicating about new initiatives.

C. Sustainable practices, products and services

Ibrahim et al. (2023) reiterated that promoting economic sustainability in construction includes reducing overall cost, while maintaining function by identifying and removing unnecessary materials and using local materials to save importation and transportation costs. PHEIs can save resources by adopting sustainable building design that integrates TBL performance indicators, including humanitarian, environmental and budgetary. They can achieve this by assessing the benefits of implementing life cycle assessment and life cycle cost analysis and accounting for the health and wellbeing of staff and students in educational buildings. Moreover, they can adopt more comprehensive and empirical research of green practices that can enhance building performance to yield more useful outputs in such areas as economy, environment, architecture and psychology.

There are several ways that firms can make an impact on people and better serve future generations through various sustainable practices that benefit society and the planet (Miller, 2020). To have significant socioenvironmental impact, PHEIs can practise fair hiring practices and encourage volunteerism at the workplace. Further, they can look externally to bring change on a larger scale by forming strategic partnerships with nonprofit organizations that share common purpose-driven goals. Adopting the TBL is pragmatic in a world that emphasizes profitability; research has shown that it is possible for firms to enjoy high profit margins by incorporating social responsibility and environmental safety (Miller, 2020). In the context of PHEIs, the TBL will not inherently bring societal and environmental impact at the expense of their financial profitability; instead, their profitability can be increased by committing to sustainable business practices. In brief, it is possible for PHEIs to address the ethical-moral issues and make money simultaneously; addressing the world's problems can indeed help them earn millions worth of economic opportunities in the long run.

Nowadays, stakeholders are increasingly willing to pay a premium for sustainable products and services (Miller, 2020). In the context of PHEIs, many students, parents and other stakeholders have become purpose-driven individuals who prefer a tertiary education that is aligned with their core values. Beyond capitalizing on an ever-expanding market for higher education, PHEIs that embrace sustainable operational strategies can greatly attract both local and international investors. By adopting the TBL, they can also become publicly more accountable in terms of internal, environmental and social governance (ESG), thus enabling them to reap higher financial returns since investors are increasingly underscoring ESG for their investment decisions.

As the world's most pressing challenges evolve, corporations need purpose-driven leaders to spearhead initiatives that can spur positive change even though making those changes seems insurmountable (Miller, 2020). In the context of PHEIs, the TBL requires tremendous courage, perseverance and commitment to achieve long-term outcomes. PHEIs need vision and purpose, beyond simply making profits, to initiate the first move. Although the journey is long and uncertain, they can start with individual students or staff to gradually rally around a common cause to bring a real, measurable impact. For example, they can cultivate TBL values on campus to create a shared purpose that will make them become more productive and innovative. Moreover, many PHEIs are currently grappling with significant challenges, often due to a misalignment in their TBL approach. To thrive as higher education exporters, they need to measure success in terms of operational and academic employment impact, while ensuring that their graduates are employable in a knowledge and digital economy (The Learnwell Projects, 2024).

D. Example of TBL

Posthumus (2013) provided a good example of an organization (furniture manufacturing) that adopts the TBL. It takes a lot of effort to recycle, reuse or sell most of the waste generated from its furniture manufacturing operations to reduce overall environmental impact and ensure that they have enough materials to continue manufacturing furniture in the future, while maximizing profits. Additionally, it invests huge sums of money into the local community by funding environmental education initiatives, local university development and general social capital-building activities in the region. Consequently, the community becomes better informed and educated about its business practices and sustainability. In turn, it values the organization for its efforts in providing jobs and learns why the larger community can benefit from environmentally conscious decisions and actions. Therefore, organizational concept is very important for PHEIs; conceptualizing higher education in terms of the TBL can help foster powerful educational programs and develop meaningful experiences for students, while saving cost for innovative ventures.

III. IMPLICATIONS

A. PHEIs in Malaysia

In Malaysia, many PHEIs are experiencing tremendous academic and financial pressure to perform better because of frozen budgets, program cuts and staff retrenchment; more than 200 had closed since 1990 because of low student numbers and inability to cover their fixed cost. The long-standing challenges culminating in these problems were exacerbated by the pandemic and other global issues (Chin et al., 2024). As aforementioned, PHEIs need to operate on the TBL in terms of operations, academic offerings and employability. First, they need to attract enough students to confront intense competition. Second, they need to maintain high academic standards to improve their rankings to attract more parents, stakeholders and other investors. Third, to become institutions of choice, they need to demonstrate that their graduates have the competencies and generic attributes for career success. Additionally, PHEIs need to organize their success metrics according to three essential dimensions, including operational, academic and career readiness. This method enables them to distil their multifaceted operations into a manageable and holistic assessment, thus helping them to make more strategic decisions and target improvements. In brief, the TBL enables PHEIs to thrive in a private equity industry in terms of profit maximization, shareholder value and spiritual or moral-ethical endeavours (The Learnwell Projects, 2024).

As aforementioned, since the 1990s, more than 200 PHEIs in Malaysia had closed mainly because they were unable to keep their enrolment high enough to cover operational costs (Chin, et al., 2024). Therefore, many PHEIs can no longer singularly focus on student enrolment as their only bottom line because they are often unable to enrol enough students to gain profitability. To cut cost, some may also be compelled to compromise academic standards and culture that undermine their other bottom line, that is, to ensure that their graduates possess the hard and generic attributes to gain employability. It is also unacceptable for faculty members, who have invested greatly in their education and training, to compromise their teaching quality for the sake of enrolment numbers and cost-saving. Moreover, PHEIs should not try to cut cost by replacing full-time faculty with adjuncts just to improve their operational bottom line in the short run because it will subsequently diminish their academic culture bottom line, which will lead to institutional decline in the long run. PHEIs that lack full-time faculty will also be short of mentors and role models for students, which will ultimately ruin its campus culture and reputation.

B. Complementary bottom lines

PHEIs need to ensure that their bottom lines complement each other; therefore, their academic standards should meet enrolment targets and attain high employability outcomes for financial stability. Bottom lines that complement each other can contribute synergistically, while enhancing their overall performance and reputation. Further, PHEIs that set higher academic standards can promote better employment outcomes, which in turn, help them attract more students and other stakeholders. Preparing newly enrolled students to thrive academically can increase their student retention, while promoting employability in the long run and establishing a positive feedback loop. To address the TBL dilemma, PHEIs need to redefine what better performance means, while balancing operational, academic and employment goals. This alignment is crucial for overcoming financial and employment challenges, ultimately leading to sustainable success. Additionally, educators and administrators need to engage in reflective practices to evaluate and align their institutions'

goals. PHEIs can only thrive by fostering a culture that prioritizes academic competence, operational efficiency and employment impact (The Learnwell Projects, 2024).

Organizations need to make a perspective shift, focus on metrics, prioritize stakeholder needs, practise strategic alignment and assess potential achievements to become stronger and more resilient than ever (The Learnwell Projects, 2024). First, PHEIs need to modify their perspectives, narratives or compromises to align their TBL metrics. Second, they need to determine which bottom line metric they can prioritize the most: operational, academic, or employment. Third, to determine which specific metric and how it impacts overall alignment, they need to focus on various stakeholders (faculty, administrators, business leaders, athletic coaches, etc.). Fourth, they need to examine if they have appropriately aligned their current operational, academic and employment bottom lines as well as their most viable strategies. Lastly, they need to evaluate their potential achievements that they can reach when their metrics are well-aligned.

C. Green efforts

Chapman (n. d.) reiterated that the TBL makes both sense and cents since it has become increasingly clear that environmentally sustainable green schools offer promises to save cost, promote academic achievement and enhance wellbeing. PHEIs can achieve tangible results from various green efforts. By focusing on people, profit and the planet simultaneously, they can account for their human or social impacts, economic benefits and environmental consequences. While our planet faces grave danger, PHEIs can help address key policy questions, regardless of politics or ideology, to provide high quality educational environments. Most importantly, green PHEIs can save cost in many ways than one. By being conscious of energy usage and taking advantage of energy efficient technologies, PHEIs have the potential to significantly reduce their electricity use, save cost and reduce their carbon footprint. By saving funds through energy efficiency and a vigorous embrace of renewable energy, they can then allocate more funds to meet more pressing educational needs.

In line with TBL, educational facilities need to provide good indoor air quality and classroom acoustics that can enhance student and teacher performance. Controlling exposure to damaging indoor environmental factors, such as carbon monoxide, dust and pollen, can help prevent respiratory diseases, while ensuring overall health improvement rate (Green Education Foundation, 2023). PHEIs can have good indoor air quality and acoustics to promote healthful living and effective functioning among students, faculty and other staff, while reducing disease-related absenteeism. With their reliance on average daily attendance rates to receive tuition fees, improved attendance is of particular importance to PHEIs. Moreover, PHEIs that strive to eliminate harmful chemicals, often found in paint, flooring, furniture, as well as conventional cleaning, pest management and dust removal products, can help eliminate eye, nose and throat irritation among staff and students. Besides removing harmful environmental factors, optimizing classroom acoustics promotes effective listening, which is a primary foundation for learning, besides reducing vocal strain among academics. Lastly, by performing in a high-performing acoustic environment, both students and teachers have greater opportunities for effective interpersonal communication, which encourages active participation and instils a sense of pride amongst students.

D. Physical infrastructure

With reference to the TBL, it is important to construct a functional bridge between built and human environments that allow educational institutions to operate at peak efficiency, while increasing their ability to meet stakeholder objectives. A competitive edge occurs when they can provide the physical infrastructure that accommodate both students and faculty (Stack, 2012). PHEIs can influence or lead institutional strategy by providing a progressive workplace and cutting-edge environment for students and faculty; hence, they can adopt facilities, strategies and programs that can lead transformational change throughout the institution and into the community. Stack (2012) added that it is crucial for educational institutions to recognize their own right and how they can help drive innovation by adapting to changing academic and business needs, such as asset restructuring and re-engineering. PHEIs can provide a healthy workplace that is conducive to faculty for innovation and assimilation of new technologies into their existing assets. Lastly, they can promote stewardship over external and internal resources that can lead to environmentally sustainable practices. In brief, PHEIs need to demonstrate to stakeholders their knowledge of maintaining and improving their asset value over time.

E. Environmental education

PHEIs can continually evaluate their programs to find better ways to achieve sustainability in today's low-budget and high-stakes educational environment. Educators and administrators need to be more inventive in tapping into the entrepreneurial business-minded spirit within each staff to promote environment-based education. PHEIs can use environmental education at a districtwide level, teach about sustainability and stewardship, while meeting curriculum content standards and benchmarks at no additional cost. Students, faculty and administrators can collaborate to identify costly environmental issues facing a district, create plans to teach about those issues and then solve those issues through service-learning projects and relevant activities that promote environmental conscience. Moreover, they can use the cost savings to introduce more sustainable and environmentally friendly operations; for example, they can develop a curriculum to introduce science concepts integrating water and carbon-cycle, non-point source pollution, human impact and sustainability to become greener. Additionally, PHEIs can engage in a service-learning project and propose a plan to reduce their district's high-maintenance green spaces by saving water, fuel and money. They can use geography and mathematics to plot a map, calculate surface areas of green space and determine the volume of water or gasoline used annually to keep the lawns green. Lastly, PHEIs can encourage students to write persuasive essays to building administrators and school board members by (1) informing them of a plan to be more sustainable and save money, (2) proposing informational materials to advocate for fertilizer and water use reduction, (3) creating marketing materials and (4) recruiting volunteers and donors to help install low maintenance native plants, trees and other natural features. Overall, by practising the TBL, PHEIs can help reduce their environmental footprint, engage students in relevant and meaningful educational experiences that foster critical thinking and problem solving and save money by reducing maintenance costs. With the combined effort of students, teachers, administrators and the surrounding community, they can provide sustainability education that encourage students and staff to innovate, solve problems, be creative and think outside the box.

F. Sustainable graduate business programs

As graduate business programs influence the next generation of corporate leaders, they need to adopt the TBL as a core tenet to produce ethical and thoughtful business leaders who focus on social and environmental impact besides financial gain (University of San Diego, 2024). PHEIs that embrace sustainable business strategies often experience several positive outcomes. First, they will enjoy more investor engagement since they are increasingly seeking to partner with businesses that prioritize social responsibility. Second, they will have better staff retention since people-focused business models often reduce employee turnover and decrease costs related to hiring and onboarding. Third, they will enjoy increased long-term profitability since investment in sustainable practices often increase overall return on investment. Lastly, by incorporating social responsibility into their curricula, they can make a favourable impact on society, the environment and stakeholders, while preparing future leaders who can display a greater sense of responsibility toward society.

Today, businesses cannot merely comply to environmental regulations; they need to strive to be environmental stewards (University of San Diego, 2024). With the increasing relevance of environmental stewardship, PHEIs need to produce promising business professionals who understand the practicality of eco-friendly practices and their long-term beneficial impact on corporate success. They need to offer specialized courses to impart environmental consciousness among future leaders by highlighting innovative, sustainable strategies, while emphasizing the long-term benefits of preserving our borrowed and shared planet. Additionally, PHEIs can use the TBL to act as the bridge between theory and practice, thus enabling graduates to understand and develop strategies that factor in profit, people and the planet. In brief, they can produce graduates who are grounded in the TBL to navigate the complex, multidimensional challenges and opportunities of the ever-changing corporate world, while balancing short-term economic interests with longer-term social and environmental goals.

Graduates equipped with a degree that prioritizes the TBL will enjoy several advantages in the job market, including greater employability, job diversity, career progression, meaningful work and future-proof careers (University of San Diego, 2024). First, they will experience greater employability as companies try to meet the increasing societal and global demands for sustainable business practices; they need professionals who are poised to fill the emerging roles. Second, TBL-focused graduates can apply their knowledge across sectors, from sustainability consulting to supply chain

management, ethical sourcing and other sustainability roles. Third, TBL-skilled graduates with a strong foundation in sustainable business practices are well-positioned to climb the corporate ladder since companies value employees who can steer them toward a triple win, including economic gains, social betterment and environmental sustainability. Fourth, TBL-conscious graduates will be able to assume roles that align with personal values and contribute positively to society, thus resulting in higher job satisfaction and improved mental wellbeing. Lastly, they will have future-proof careers; with businesses increasingly adopting sustainable and socially responsible practices, they are ready to take on the jobs of the future.

G. Corporate social responsibility

As corporate social responsibility (CSR) becomes increasingly important, the use of the TBL to address social and environmental issues has also gained momentum. Moreover, CSR aligns well with the TBL, which requires organizations to measure their performance by considering their impacts on people and planet. Firms that put people and the planet at the heart of their business, on par with profits, are not only doing the appropriate thing, but will also reap several business benefits (Farnham, 2023). In the contexts of PHEIs, CSR can improve corporate culture, foster favourable relationships and augment business performance. First, it can make employee attraction and retention easier, increase employee engagement and loyalty and capitalize on a more diverse and inclusive workforce. Second, a PHEI's ethical performance is a purchasing consideration (enrolment) for a significant number of consumers (students). By creating an organization where integrity, society and the environment genuinely matter, PHEIs can establish a reputation that attracts students and potential hires. Third, while profits are an important dimension of the TBL, PHEIs that pay attention to the other two dimensions (people and planet) will also demonstrate better financial performance than others.

Farnham (2023) added that firms that practise CSR can minimize regulatory compliance and governance risk, strengthen their supply chain and make better investment propositions. In the context of PHEIs, reporting on environmental, social and governance (ESG) issues is increasingly becoming best practice, with penalties for noncompliance. Failings in such areas as pollution and employee wellbeing can incur hefty fines, remediation costs and reputational damage. Second, adopting sustainable supply chains is not just a good practice for PHEIs, it can also increase the robustness of their operations and make the institution less vulnerable to the effects of business interruption (such as the pandemic and declining enrolment). Third, with ESG performance increasingly transparent and ESG scores a core consideration for potential investors, it makes sound business sense for PHEIs to pay greater attention to their impact on people and the planet.

H. University social responsibility

Alzyoud and Bani-Hani (2015) asserted that universities have the social responsibility to strengthen civil commitment and active citizenship; provide services to the community through community engagement and outreach; foster economic and national development; promote ethical approaches to address critical issues; develop a sense of civil citizenship by encouraging students and staff to provide social services to their local community; promote ecological or environmental commitment for local and global sustainable development; to develop local and global human resources; expand human knowledge through quality research and education for the nation and for humanity. Therefore, PHEIs can implement a policy on ethical quality of their campus community via the responsible management of their educational, cognitive, labour and environmental impacts to promote sustainable human development.

University social responsibility can be put into practice when their leaders emphasize the importance of public responsibility, ethical behaviour and good citizenship (Alzyoud & Bani-Hani, 2015). Therefore, the top management of PHEIs should act as role models who care about community health, safety, and the environment. They can support important public issues that are within the boundaries and resources of the institution, for example, by improving education in the community, pursuing environmental excellence, practising resource conservation, promoting and improving the health of the community, performing community service, conducting research to generate socioeconomic development and providing guidelines for the development and sustainability of society. They can also influence other organizations, whether private or public, to form partnerships to address critical issues and concerns.

Additionally, CSR is a good platform for any private corporation to contribute back to the society (Senin, Halim & Ali, 2019); therefore, PHEIs can be a strategic platform to help society in terms of quality education. Helping to improve and innovate the education system in the country is not only beneficial for students, but also for academics, administrators and

parents because every party can gain experience and collaborate in providing sustainable education. Moreover, CSR activities and involvement in the education sector can be expanded to every private corporation to help the government in realizing its educational blueprint. On the other hand, the government can also plan more initiatives to support and encourage PHEIs to align their CSR and ESG efforts with their profit margins.

Universities can foster skills that will influence the ethical behaviours and decisions of graduates so that they can effectively respond to the real world. In the corporate sector, ethical commitment is articulated through CSR; therefore, it is crucial to know how students perceive their university's ethical instruction, factors influencing it and their orientation toward CSR. Rodríguez-Gómez et al. (2022) found that ethical instruction, family education and values and social vision were positively and significantly related to the students' orientation toward CSR. The researchers implied that family education focusing on positive values should be taken into account in the ethical instruction of future university students; hence, PHEIs should equip future business leaders with the values and capabilities needed to promote actions that lead to the generation of sustainable value for businesses and for the society at large.

IV. CONCLUSION

To conclude this conceptual paper, a TBL case study was carried out at Jesselton University College (JUC) in Sabah, Malaysia. JUC, the first homegrown college that achieved university college status in Sabah, focuses and commits to equity on campus, supporting students and staff culturally with various social, cultural and sports events. Additionally, it tries to find ways to benefit all stakeholders, including staff, students, parents and the greater community by creating a reciprocal social structure that interconnects general wellbeing, labour interests, corporate interests and social welfare. Further, JUC's compulsory subject, "Moral Education" underscores the ways that higher education can promote environmental and social justice, diversity, equity and inclusion in its endeavour to foster a more stable and better society for everyone. Lastly, the college regards everybody as a global citizen who can make a difference in terms of sustainability, both individually and collectively (Chin & Yong, 2024).

At JUC, it is all about balancing business, helping people and preserving the environment. Profit-wise, JUC offers courses that are highly affordable to attract students. Additionally, it provides needy students with free accommodation and transport, while charging lower fees for students from the rural and underserved areas. By making education affordable, it helps students from disadvantaged backgrounds get the same educational opportunities as others. People-wise, JUC provides financial assistance to students, especially bumiputra (indigenous) students from Sabah. For example, it accepts students who have received a RM16,000 government loan even though the real fees is RM27,000. Besides resume and portfolio writing, it offers internships and assists fresh graduates to seek gainful employment. With a passion for aesthetics, JUC operates a floral shop that specializes in flower arrangements and gifts. Besides being a leading provider of premium floral products and services in the area, it also provides free floral arrangement classes to homemakers and senior citizens. Planet-wise, JUC has initiated a plastic-free campus by getting everyone to make the place greener through recycling, reusing and reducing things. Moreover, it encourages staff to go paperless for internal communications or print on both sides to save paper. Lastly, it organizes green campaigns annually, which include jungle trekking, litter removal on roadsides and beach cleaning (Chin & Yong, 2024).

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